

Application of MADM Methods for Machinability study of Magnetic Abrasive Finishing Process for the Evaluation of Surface Finish

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Abstract

The aim of the present study is to apply preference selection index (PSI) method for selection of optimal process parameters of Magnetic Abrasive Finishing Process (MAF) for Stainless-steel SS316 Material. Experts or users related to MAF technology are always interested to select an appropriate optimal process parameters involved in finishing of component which directly affect the response process parameters such as magnetic flux density, rotational speed of the work-piece, machining gap, mesh size of the abrasives and percentage weight of abrasives etc. In present study one case study is considered from them literature to study the suitability of PSI method for selection of MAF process parameter for Stainless-steel SS316 Material.

Keywords: MAF Process, Stainless-steel SS316 Material, PSI Method.

1. Introduction

Magnetic Abrasive Finishing (MAF) process has an important advanced machining technique which is used to manufacture intricate shapes with great accuracy and good surface finish. In MAF, the workpiece is subjected to a controlled magnetic field, guiding abrasive particles to remove material from the surface. The process can be tailored for various finishing profiles, including cylindrical, inner, and plane surfaces. MAF is characterized by its ability to produce high-quality surfaces with improved roughness, leading to enhanced functionality and performance of manufactured components. This method is especially relevant in industries where precision and excellence in surface quality are paramount. The versatility of MAF allows for the efficient finishing of diverse materials, including stainless-steel SS316, super-alloys, composites and advanced ceramics. Jain et al., (2001) investigated the effect of working gap and circumferential speed on material removal, change in surface finish and percent improvement in surface finish. It

was found that material removal decreases by increasing working gap or decreasing circumferential speed of the workpiece. Wang et al., (2005) investigated the finishing of tubes made of three kinds of materials such as Ly12 aluminum alloy, 316L stainless steel and H62 brass. Experimental results indicated that finishing parameters such as speed, abrasive material, magnetic abrasive manufacturing process and grain size have critical effects on the material removal rate (MRR). They also demonstrated the inner surface micro shape changes during finishing of turned aluminum tube. The researchers Mulik and Pandey (2010), Singh et al. (2006) Singh et al. (2004), Jain et al. (2001) used fixed Fe particle size of 300 mesh number for better performance. Sharma and Bhardwaj (2014) investigated the internal finishing of stainless steel 304L using a sintered magnetic abrasive powder (70% Fe and 30% Silicon Carbide). They obtained maximum percentage improvement in surface finish of 94%. The possibility of free form surface polishing has been confirmed by MFAAF process because it has flexibility of profiling and does not need any complex tool path control with respect to the workpiece surface. Vasantha et al., (2020) Studied on experimentation with various process parameters which were reduced the surface roughness value on a cylindrical component. These studies also show that in order to obtain a better surface finish, in addition to hardness, the initial roughness of the workpiece needs to be considered. The present study shows that on various parameters of machining, improvement in surface finish is maximum in case of brass as compared to other materials.

In addition, some applications of MADM methods were reported in the literature related to selection of MAF process in the literature. Gadakh. V. S. et al., (2011) presented application of multi-objective optimization on the basis of ratio analysis. MOORA method is applied for solving multiple criteria (objective) optimization problem in milling process. A. Babbar et al., (2022) Studied that parameters are successfully optimized for the surface roughness and material removal rate using the multi objective grey relational analysis (GRA) technique. M. Vahdati et al., (2016) applied RSM Method and evaluate the parameters affecting to MAF on Concave Freeform Surface of Al Alloy. Byun et al., (2005) applied the modified TOPSIS method for selection of various rapid prototyping processes. Pate et al. (2015) applied MOORA method and TOPSIS method for evaluation of FDM process parameters.

Aim of this present study is to apply the PSI method for the selection of optimal process parameter of MAF process applied on Stainless steel SS-316 material. The responses considered in present study are mechanical property of MAF produced such as material removal rate (MRR), surface roughness (SR) and micro hardness.

2. Solution Methodology (PSI Method)

This section describes PSI method for selection of appropriate process parameter for MAF process. The PSI method developed by Maniya and Bhatt [15] for solving the multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) problems. In PSI method, it is not necessary to assign relative importance between attributes. Moreover, there is no requirement of computing the weights of attributes involved in decision making problems in this method. This method is useful when there is a conflict in deciding the relative importance among attributes. The main steps of the proposed model are described below.

Step-1: Identify the problem.

Determine objective and identify the pertinent attributes and alternatives involved in the decision-making problem under consideration. Let $A = \{A_i \text{ for } i=1, 2, 3, \dots, m\}$ be a set of MAF process alternative, $B = \{B_j \text{ for } j=1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ be a set of decision criteria or attributes of MAF process alternatives selection problem, and x_{ij} is the performance of alternative A_i when it is examined with criteria B_j .

Step-2: Formulate the decision matrix.

In this step involves construction of a matrix based on all the information available that describes the problem attributes. Each row of decision matrix is allocated to one alternative and each column to one attribute. Therefore, an element X_{ij} of the decision matrix X gives the value of the j^{th} attribute in original real values; that is a non-normalized form and units for the i^{th} alternative. There are shown in table 1. Thus, if the number of alternatives is M and the number of attributes is N , then the decision matrix as an $N \cdot M$ matrix can be represented as follows:

Table 1. Decision matrix

Alternatives	Criteria			
	C_1	C_2	C_n
A_1	X_{11}	X_{12}	X_{1n}
A_2	X_{21}	X_{22}	X_{2n}
:	:	:	:	:
:	:	:	:	:
A_m	X_{m1}	X_{m2}	X_{mn}

Step-3: Normalization the data.

In the multi-attribute decision making methods it is required to make the attribute value dimensionless. For this purpose, the attribute values are transformed into 0 and 1. This process of transforming is known as normalization, which is done on the basis of the type of the attribute. If the attribute is beneficial type, then larger values are desired, which can be normalized as:

$$N_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{X_{jmax}} \quad (1)$$

If the attributes is non-beneficial type, then smaller values are desired, which can be normalized as:

$$N_{ij} = \frac{X_{jmax}}{X_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

Where X_{ij} is the attribute measure ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, M$).

Step-4: Compute the mean value of the normalized data.

In this step, mean value of the normalized data of every attribute is computed by the following equation:

$$N = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n N_{ij} \quad (3)$$

Step-5: Compute the preference variation value.

In this step, a preference variation value between the values of every attribute is computed using the following equation:

$$\phi_j = \sum_{i=1}^n [N_{ij} - N]^2 \quad (4)$$

Step-6: Determine the deviation in preference value.

In this step, deviation in the preference value is computed for every attribute using the following equation:

$$\Omega_j = [1 - \phi_j] \quad (5)$$

Step-7: Compute the overall preference value.

In this step of PSI method, overall preference value is determined for every attribute using the following equation:

$$\omega_j = \frac{\Omega_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n \Omega_j} \quad (6)$$

Moreover, the total overall preference value of all the attributes should be one i.e., $\sum_{j=1}^m \Omega_j$

Step-8: Compute the preference selection index.

Now, the preference selection index is calculated for each alternative using the following equation:

$$\theta_i = \sum_{j=1}^m N_{ij} \times \omega_j \quad (7)$$

Step-9: Select the appropriate alternative for the given application.

Each alternative is ranked according to descending or ascending order to facilitate the managerial interpretation of the results. The alternative having the highest preference selection index will be ranked first and so on.

3. Illustration of Example Using AHP/MOORA Method

Step 1: Determine the objective and identify the pertinent attributes and alternatives involved in the decision-making problem under consideration. Here, total twenty-seven alternatives are considered which represents the response of experiment numbers and three criteria are considered which represents the output of MAF process applied on Stainless steel SS-316 material.

Step 2: Formulate the Decision Matrix: as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Decision matrix

Alternative	Surface Roughness (RA- μm)	Material Removal Rate	Micro Hardness
A1	49.566	0.001	55.916
A2	49.102	0.001	53.368
A3	50.089	0.001	52.174
A4	40.874	0.002	62.710
A5	40.169	0.002	61.742
A6	40.802	0.002	60.645
A7	37.616	0.002	69.548
A8	37.311	0.002	67.548
A9	37.841	0.002	66.561
A10	46.608	0.002	65.981
A11	46.093	0.002	63.310
A12	46.819	0.002	63.142
A13	39.495	0.002	72.452
A14	39.176	0.002	71.161
A15	40.133	0.002	69.626
A16	34.954	0.003	73.032
A17	34.285	0.003	71.787
A18	35.394	0.003	70.819
A19	39.656	0.003	75.981
A20	39.195	0.003	74.503
A21	39.884	0.003	73.245
A22	37.702	0.003	75.981
A23	37.184	0.003	73.529
A24	37.932	0.003	72.432
A25	33.244	0.004	84.723
A26	32.294	0.004	82.665
A27	33.295	0.003	81.181

Step3: The decision matrix is normalized using Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) depending upon the type of data. Normalized decision matrix is shown in Table 3. Here Surface Roughness is non-beneficial type, and then small values are desired, where material removal rate and micro hardness are beneficial type, and then large values are desired.

$$N_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij}}{x_{jmax}} \quad N_{11} = \frac{0.001}{0.004} = 0.004$$

Here Surface Roughness is non-beneficial type, and then small values are desired, which can be normalized using Eq. (2) and all normalized value shows in Table 3.

$$N_{ij} = \frac{X_{ijmin}}{X_{ij}} \quad N_{15} = \frac{32.294}{59.566} = 0.652$$

Table 3. Normalize Decision Matrix

Alternative	Surface Roughness (RA- μ m)	Material Removal Rate	Micro Hardness
A1	0.652	0.211	0.660
A2	0.658	0.171	0.630
A3	0.645	0.184	0.616
A4	0.790	0.474	0.740
A5	0.804	0.526	0.729
A6	0.791	0.395	0.716
A7	0.859	0.526	0.821
A8	0.866	0.605	0.797
A9	0.853	0.579	0.786
A10	0.693	0.579	0.779
A11	0.701	0.526	0.747
A12	0.690	0.526	0.745
A13	0.818	0.632	0.855
A14	0.824	0.605	0.840
A15	0.805	0.579	0.822
A16	0.924	0.711	0.862
A17	0.942	0.763	0.847
A18	0.912	0.684	0.836
A19	0.814	0.816	0.897
A20	0.824	0.842	0.879
A21	0.810	0.895	0.865
A22	0.857	0.684	0.897
A23	0.868	0.737	0.868
A24	0.851	0.711	0.855
A25	0.971	1.000	1.000
A26	1.000	0.921	0.976

A27	0.970	0.895	0.958
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Step4: Computethe meanvalueofthenormalizeddatausingEq.(3)anditsvaluesaresameas findthevalue of $\dot{N}_1=0.8219, \dot{N}_2=0.6213, \dot{N}_3=0.8156$.

$$N = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n N_{ij}$$

Step5: Now,a preferencevariationvalue forMAFprocessparameter selectionattributes are ComputedusingEq.(4), anditsvaluesare; $\emptyset_1=0.256, \emptyset_2=1.204, \emptyset_3=0.244$.

$$\emptyset_j = \sum_{i=1}^n [N_{ij} - N]^2$$

$$\emptyset_1 = 0.256$$

Step6: ThedeviationinapreferencevariationvalueiscomputedforMAFprocessparameter selectionattributesusingEq.(5),anditsvaluesare; $11=0.8914, 12=0.8146, 13=0.5820, 14=0.8060, 15=0.7593$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_j &= [1 - \emptyset_j] \\ \Omega_j &= [1 - 0.256] \Omega_j \\ &= 0.744 \end{aligned}$$

Step7: ComputetheoverallpreferencevalueisdeterminedforeveryattributeusingtheEq.(6)and its values are; $\omega_1=0.574, \omega_2=0.158, \omega_3=0.584$.

$$\omega_j = \frac{\Omega_j}{\sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n \Omega_j}$$

$$\omega_1 = 0.574$$

Step8: Thepreference selectionindex is computed by Eq.(7)and itsresultsareshowninTable4.

$$\theta_i = \sum_{j=1}^m N_{ij} \times \omega_j$$

$$\theta_1 = 0.726$$

Table4.PreferenceSelectionIndex

Alternative	θ_{15}	Rank
A1	0.726	2
A2	0.718	2
A3	0.701	2
A4	0.811	1
A5	0.804	2
A6	0.810	2
A7	0.889	8
A8	0.867	1
A9	0.857	1
A10	0.761	2
A11	0.755	2
A12	0.748	2
A13	0.869	1
A14	0.868	1
A15	0.850	1
A16	0.921	4
A17	0.915	5
A18	0.904	7
A19	0.862	1
A20	0.853	1
A21	0.828	1
A22	0.907	6
A23	0.889	9
A24	0.876	1
A25	0.984	2
A26	0.998	1
A27	0.975	3

4. Results & Discussion

The results obtained for evaluation and selection of MAF process parameter using application of PSI method is presented in Table 4. Ranking of all 27 alternatives is carried out based on PSI method. According to performed experimental design, it is clearly observed that experimenter alternative number 26 gives the best multi-performance features of the MAF process among the 27 experiments..

5. Conclusion

In the present work the application of PSI method is illustrated for selection of MAF process parameter. It is found that the PSI method is very simple to understand and easy to implement. In a literature review on these existing MADM methods, it is revealed that it is necessary to assign the relative importance between attributes or weights of attributes are required. For this, generally AHP or entropy method is used for computing the weights. But in PSI method, there is no need to calculate the relative weight of attributes. E.g., v in case of VIKOR method and ζ in case of GRA method.

All these reasons have made the PSI method as a highly stable method for solving the decision-making problems. Henceforth, it may be helpful to the decision makers having less experienced for deciding weight of attributes. PSI method can be used for any number of attributes. For this reason, the PSI method is highly stable for many decision-making problems. The PSI method gives directly optimal solution without assigning the relative importance between materials selection attributes and it is the beauty of PSI method.

References

- [1] Jain V. K., Kumar P., Behera P.K., and Jayswal S. C., "Effect of Working Gap and Circumferential Speed on The Performance of Magnetic Abrasive Finishing Process", *Wear*, 250, 2001, pp 384-390.
- [2] Wang, Y and D. Hu., "Study on the inner surface finishing of tubing by magnetic abrasive finishing", *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, Vol. 45, No.1, 2005, pp. 43-49.
- [3] Mulik, R.S. and P.M. Pandey., "Mechanism of surface finishing in ultrasonic assisted magnetic abrasive finishing process", *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, Vol. 25, No. 12, 2010, pp. 1418-1427.
- [4] Singh, D.K., V.K. Jain and V. Raghuram., "Experimental investigations into forces acting during a magnetic abrasive finishing process", *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, Vol. 30, No. 7-8, 2006, pp. 652-662.
- [5] Singh, D.K., V.K. Jain and V. Raghuram., "Parametric study of magnetic abrasive finishing process, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, Vol. 149, No. 1, 2004, pp. 22–29.
- [6] Jain, N.K. and V.K. Jain., "Modeling of material removal in mechanical type advanced machining processes: a state-of-art review", *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, Vol. 41, 2001, pp. 1573-1635.
- [7] Sharma, R. and H. Bhardwaj., "Internal Finishing of Stainless-steel Cylinders Using Magnetic Abrasive Finish Method", *International Journal of Scientific Research and Education*, Vol. 2, No. 8, 2014, pp. 1512-1521.
- [8] Vasantha Prasath N, Abdul Gaffar T, Vasanth A., "Performance Characteristics of Magnetic Abrasive Finishing (MAF) of Al 4061", *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)* ISSN: 2278-0181, Vol. 9 Issue 02, February-2020, pp 61-65
- [9] Gadakh. V. S., "Application of MOORA method for parametric optimization of milling Process", *International journal of applied engineering research*, Dindigul, ISSN - 0976-4259, 2011, Volume 1, No 4
- [10] A. Babbar, A. Sharma and P. Singh, Multi-objective optimization of magnetic abrasive finishing using grey relational analysis, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.01.004>
- [11] M. Vahdati and SeyedAlireza Rasouli, "Evaluation of Parameters Affecting Magnetic Abrasive Finishing on Concave Freeform Surface of Al Alloy via RSM Method", *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, Volume 2016, Article ID 5256347, 2016, 14 pages <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2016/5256347>
- [12] H.S. Byun, "A decision support system for the selection of a rapid prototyping process using the modified TOPSIS method", *Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol.* 26(2005)1338-1347.
- [13] P.B. Patel, J.D. Patel, K.D. Maniya KD, Evaluation of FDM process parameter for polylactic acid material using MOORA-TOPSIS method. *I. J. Mech. Ind. Technol.* 3 84-93(2015).
- [14] K.D. Maniya, M.G. Bhatt, A selection of material using a novel type of decision-making method Preference selection index method. *Mater. Des.* 3 (2010) 1785–1789